

USE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN
FORMING SELF-DEVELOPMENT COMPETENCY IN PRIMARY CLASS
MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the specific methods and importance of communication from information communication in the management of self-development compensa in production class mother tongue and pre-school classes. Today, the organization of effective use of information and communication technologies and the Internet is one of the most important productions. Production of the 5 important initiatives adopted "On raising the morale of young people and meaningfully organizing free time" in the production population and organization of computer technologies and the Internet in the youth association.

Keywords: competence, knowledge, skill, competence, opinion, video, multimedia, disc, video.

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Decision No. 187 of April 6, 2017 "On harmonization of state educational standards of general secondary education and secondary special, vocational education" is being implemented today. In order to put into practice the state educational standards that are conducive to the production of competence, each pedagogue must first carefully study the DTS and the curriculum of his subject and draw up a future plan based on this. To clearly define and produce the basic and subject-related competencies that will be formed in the pupils in the technology field of the lesson. At the same time, the pedagogue should have the ability to determine whether these competencies have been formed in pupils. Designation of educational technologies for the use of competencies in pupils has a great place. Competence education is the demand of today's education. When the young generation that we educate and educate does not stumble at the threshold of life, but meets It is necessary for them to grow up to be well-rounded people who are able to solve problems independently, use modern technical tools easily, communicate with people without difficulty and without hesitation, and have their own place in society as a person. It is no coincidence that the reforms taking place in the field of education today are aimed at solving such urgent tasks. The effectiveness of education is reflected in the pupil's knowledge. The pupil's knowledge is determined by his ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice and in life. Today, in the process of education, special importance is attached to the fact that the pupil can solve some everyday problem from the knowledge he

acquires. Knowledge is the information given to the pupil during the educational process, skill is the ability to use this information effectively, and skill is the application of the received information in practice. Competence is the ability to apply knowledge, skills and abilities in everyday life. In addition to the special competencies that are formed based on each characteristic, the basic competencies that need to be formed in the lessons occupy an important place. Self-development competence is a person's constant physical, spiritual, mental, intellectual and creative development of himself, striving for perfection, regularly improving himself throughout life, alternative evaluation of his behavior and is manifested in the ability to make decisions. In the formation of competence, more conversations are conducted in the lessons, using information and communication technologies. It is very important to invite pupils to debate with questions like If we consider the example of one reading lesson, by reading the text in roles, the skills of expressing their relationship to the characters are formed. They describe the sequence of events consistently. It depends on the skill of the teacher to fully listen to the opinion of each elementary school pupil, to show the approval of the opinions as an example. Through this, pupils learn to evaluate adequately, learn to express their opinion freely. No matter what the freely expressed opinion is, it is important for the teacher to get them to listen to it to the end and express their feelings.

is important. Because teaching to listen to the opinion of others requires attention and responsibility from the teacher. A pupil who listens to the opinions of others will fully understand the story. Expresses one's attitude and does not repeat the opinion of others. It is one of the important tasks to explain to the pupil who expressed a wrong opinion that his opinion is not correct, to guide him to the right way of thinking. For example: in the story "Etiquette of Being a Guest" in the 1st grade Mother Language and Reading Literacy textbook, the pupil persuades the teacher to carry out a separate activity, despite the fact that the teacher says that he "learned the secrets of pottery for another year". Although his work was successful at first, in the end no one would buy it due to the fact that the secrets of his dishes quickly spread, and the pupil returned to his teacher. When discussing the story, most pupils do not approve of the pupil's work. But there may be pupils who did not approve of some of the works of the potter. They may be the ones who commented that "couldn't the teacher teach the subtle secrets of pottery until he always likes fire and moves water?" Then the teacher should direct the pupils to take a deeper look at the events without giving any wrong opinion. He should explain to the pupils that there is a time for teaching and learning everything, and that a pupil should never take the teacher's word for granted. Individuals without independent thinking have a hard time finding their own way. Therefore, educating people who have a free and independent mind, who can distinguish

good from bad, good from evil, and who can freely enter into communication is one of the main tasks of today's education and pedagogues. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies in primary school reading classes increases the effectiveness of the lesson. Any pedagogical technology should be developed logically based on the essence of a specific topic during the lesson. Through the use of advanced pedagogical and information communication technologies in classes, distinguishing academic subjects from each other, having qualities such as hard work, correctness, respect, understanding and correcting one's own mistakes. development competencies it is necessary to convey to their children that they should use opportunities effectively. As one of the famous sages said, Disterverg, "Teach the pupil to work, teach him not only to love work, to be in harmony with it in such a way that work is absorbed into his body, teach him that, for him, his own strength it should be considered unthinkable not to be able to learn something with Our forefathers have emphasized that the formation of working skills and the personal example of adults are important factors in the upbringing of a child. The educational process requires every pedagogue to search and work tirelessly on himself. Especially elementary school pupils are curious, aspiring, active. If different methods are used during the lesson, it will increase the interest of children and improve the ability to remember. Achieving this in the lessons, of course, requires research, the use of information and communication technologies. The young generation that we educate and educate does not stumble at the threshold of life, is able to independently solve the problems encountered, can easily use modern technical tools, has no difficulty in communicating with people, has a place in society as an individual. it is necessary for them to grow up as mature people. It is no coincidence that the reforms taking place in the field of education today are aimed at solving such urgent tasks.

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